

Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium Tetroxide catalysed Oxidation of Deoxybenzoin and *p*-Nitrodeoxybenzoin by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

N. C. KHANDUAL

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-753 003

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Kinetics of osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of deoxybenzoin and *p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied in 30% (v/v) *t*-butanol-water mixture at a constant ionic strength. The reaction is found to be first order each in [substrate], $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($[\text{OH}^-] < 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) but independent of [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. The rates of reaction decrease with decrease in dielectric constant and increase with increase in ionic strength of the medium. The entropy of activation is found to be negative. The mechanism involves the formation of an intermediate complex between enolate anion of deoxybenzoin and Os^{VIII} which rapidly decomposes followed by a fast reaction between the reduced osmium species and hexacyanoferrate(III).

In continuation of our earlier work on the kinetics of osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of organic substrates¹ by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), I report herein the kinetics of osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of deoxybenzoin and *p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin. The uncatalysed oxidation of deoxybenzoin by hexacyanoferrate(III) is either extremely slow or does not proceed at all. In the presence of a catalyst, like Os^{VIII} this reaction is amenable to kinetic investigation. The exact role of the osmium tetroxide in the oxidation of deoxybenzoin has not yet been shown and this prompted me to investigate the osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of deoxybenzoin and *p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

Deoxybenzoin was prepared and purified² (m.p. 58°) and *p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin was prepared according to the reported method³. Hexacyanoferrate(III), *t*-butanol, potassium chloride and potassium hydroxide were of AnalaR grade. The solution ($0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of osmium tetroxide (Johnson and Mathey) was prepared in KOH solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3}). Ionic strength was adjusted with potassium chloride.

Kinetic measurement: Reaction mixture containing the requisite quantities of deoxybenzoin, OsO_4 and KOH, and a solution of hexacyanoferrate(III) were thermally equilibrated separately for about 30 min at 30°. A known volume of hexacyanoferrate(III) was then transferred to the reaction mixture, aliquots were removed at regular time intervals and the amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) formed during the reaction was estimated by titrating against a standard solution of ceric salt using

ferroin as an indicator. The standard zero order rate constants (k_0) reported are average values of duplicate runs. No oxidation of the solvent occurred under the condition employed.

Stoichiometry: Stoichiometric investigation carried out using a known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) at 30°, showed that 1 mole of deoxybenzoin required 2 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) to give benzoin as the final product of oxidation. The tlc-pure products was characterised (ir, m.m.p.) as benzoin, m.p. 137°.

Rate laws: Since both the substrates showed identical trends, the salient results and discussion given in sequel refer to either of the substrates. The reaction is zero order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)] as shown by the constant values of k_0 over a ten-fold variation of [hexacyanoferrate(III)] (Table 1). The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in [deoxybenzoin] (Table 2), indicating the first order reaction in [deoxybenzoin]. The oxidation rate is directly proportional to [alkali] (Table 3) at low $[\text{OH}^-]$ (0.04 mol dm^{-3}) but it becomes zero order at $[\text{OH}^-] > 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate of the reaction

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)]

[Deoxybenzoin] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OsO}_4] = 1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = 30°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Solvent = 30% (v/v) <i>t</i> -butanol	k_0 $\times 10^6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$
[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	
1.0	3.80
2.0	3.80
4.0	3.60
6.0	3.60
8.0	3.38
10.0	3.30

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [DEOXYBENZZOIN]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]= 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[OsO₄]= 1.5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻]= 2.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³,
 $\mu=0.1$ mol dm⁻³; Temp.=30°,
Solvent=30% (v/v) t-butanol

[Deoxybenzoin] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k_0 × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k_0 (× 10 ³ min ⁻¹) [Deoxybenzoin]
1.0	0.75	0.75
2.0	1.41	0.70
4.0	2.98	0.74
5.0	3.80	0.76
8.0	5.69	0.71
10.0	7.53	0.75

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [OH⁻]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]= 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[OsO₄]= 1.5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, [Deoxybenzoin]= 5.0×10^{-3}
mol dm⁻³, $\mu=0.1$ mol dm⁻³, Temp.=30°, Solvent=30%
(v/v) t-butanol

[OH ⁻] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	k_0 × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k_0 (× 10 ³ min ⁻¹) [OH ⁻]
1.0	1.81	1.8
2.0	3.80	1.9
4.0	8.30	2.0
6.0	11.45	1.9
8.0	13.63	1.7
10.0	18.05	1.8

increases with the increase in catalyst concentration (Table 4). The values of k_0 /[OsO₄] are found to increase at low catalyst concentrations (6.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³) but at high catalyst concentrations the values decrease. However, to the first approximation, the

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [OsO₄]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]= 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[Deoxybenzoin]= 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[OH⁻]= 2.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, $\mu=0.1$ mol dm⁻³,
Temp.=30°, Solvent=30% (v/v) t-butanol

[OsO ₄] × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³	k_0 × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k_0 (× 10 ⁻³ min ⁻¹) [OsO ₄]
1.0	2.43	0.24
1.5	3.80	0.25
2.5	6.57	0.26
3.5	9.10	0.26
5.0	13.52	0.27
6.0	17.40	0.29
7.0	19.67	0.28
10.0	27.03	0.27
12.0	30.10	0.25
14.0	35.40	0.25
15.0	36.80	0.24

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON IONIC STRENGTH

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]= 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[Deoxybenzoin]= 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄]= 1.5×10^{-7}
mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻]= 2.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, Temp.=30°,
Solvent=30% (v/v) t-butanol

Ionic strength	k_0 × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
0.04	0.83
0.06	1.81
0.08	2.17
0.10	3.80
0.20	5.23

direct proportionality of the reaction rate at low catalyst concentration might be assumed. The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in ionic strength of the medium (Table 5) and a plot of log k_0 vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ is linear (Fig. 1) indicating ion-ion reaction. Added ferrocyanide showed no effect on the rate of oxidation.

Fig. 1. Plot of log k_0 vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ for hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of deoxybenzoin at 30°.

Solvent effect: The decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium decreases the rate constant (Table 6). The plot of log k_0 vs $1/D$ (dielectric constant of the medium) is linear (Fig. 2) which provides an additional evidence in favour of ion-ion reaction.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON RATE

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]= 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[Deoxybenzoin]= 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[OH⁻]= 2.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄]= 1.5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³,
 $\mu=0.1$ mol dm⁻³, Temp.=35°

t-Butanol % (v/v)	k_0 × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
20	7.63
30	6.30
40	4.53

Effect of temperature: The plot of log k_0 vs $1/T$ is linear. The energies and entropies of activation are found to be 42.78 kJ mol⁻¹ and -194.97 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (deoxybenzoin) and 58.65 kJ mol⁻¹ and -136.54 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (*p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin) (Table 7). The greater reactivity of deoxybenzoin over *p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin is explained on the basis that electron-attracting groups retard the reaction rate, present on the benzene nucleus.

Results and Discussion

Osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of deoxybenzoin and *p*-nitrodeoxybenzoin by alkaline hexa-

TABLE 7—REACTION RATES AND ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR ALKALINE HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) OXIDATION OF DEOXYBENZONIN AND *p*-NITRODEOXYBENZONIN IN *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURE

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]¹ = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Substrate] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 2×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄] = 1.5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³, Solvent = 30% (v/v) *t*-butanol

Substrate	$k_o (\times 10^5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1})$			E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger Jk ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
	30°	35°	40°				
Deoxybenzoin	3.80	6.30	10.47	42.78	-194.97	40.21	100.26
<i>p</i> -Nitrodeoxybenzoin	3.0	5.2	8.40	58.65	-136.54	45.50	98.50

cyanoferrate(III) is characterised by the following facts. (i) The reaction rate is independent of the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) but proportional to the concentration of deoxybenzoin, alkali and osmium tetroxide. (ii) The rate of the reaction decreases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. (iii) The reaction velocity increases with the decrease in ionic strength of the medium. (iv) The entropy of activation is found to be negative. (v) The stoichiometry of the reaction was calculated to be Δ hexacyanoferrate(III)/ Δ deoxybenzoin, 2 : 1 and the product of oxidation was found to be benzoin.

Thus under the above conditions, a probable rate law might be given as,

$$-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/dt = k[\text{deoxybenzoin}][\text{OH}^-][\text{OsO}_4]$$

In the present investigation, no induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile or reduction of HgCl₂ has been observed. Hence a free radical mechanism is ruled out. But on the other hand, the reaction is alkali-dependent, shows positive salt-effect, sensitive to dielectric constant of the solvent composition and the entropy of activation is negative. The reaction probably proceeds through an ionic mechanism involving enolate anion intermediate.

Deoxybenzoin is easily oxidised to benzoin by chromic acid⁴. The redox potential of Cr^{VI}/Cr^{III} couple is 1.36 V which is high enough to oxidise the substrate. The oxidation of the same substrate by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) on the other hand, does not proceed in the absence of the catalyst. This is possibly because the oxidation potential of hexacyanoferrate(III)/hexacyanoferrate(II) couple is very low (-0.36 V) and does not appear to differ appreciably from that of deoxybenzoin/benzoin couple, the data for which are lacking in the literature. However, the oxidising or reducing ability of a substance can be altered by diminishing the activity of the oxidised or reduced form of the redox couple and this can be achieved by the addition of a suitable complexing agent. The catalyst osmium tetroxide which is necessary to promote the reaction possibly plays a role in lowering the redox potential of deoxybenzoin/benzoin couple. It is worthwhile to mention that if only deoxybenzoin and OsO₄ are taken in alkaline medium, the colour of the osmium tetroxide immediately disappears and if this solution is acidified and titrated against standard ceric sulphate, then 2 moles of ceric are required for one mole of OsO₄. This proves that

it is the reduced osmium which is first oxidised to its original octavalent state by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). It has already been pointed out that the oxidation of deoxybenzoin with ceric sulphate is not appreciable under these conditions and hence it is possibly the Os^{VI} which reacts rapidly with hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. The alkali-dependence of oxidation process clearly indicates that the oxidation of deoxybenzoin takes place through the formation of a complex enolate anion between OsO₄ and OH⁻ ion. Since the uncatalysed oxidation does not proceed at all and hexacyanoferrate(III) is consumed without taking part in the rate law, it is assumed that hexacyanoferrate(III) does not react directly until after the rate-determining step. It is the reduced osmium which is first oxidised to its original octavalent state. Further, according to the proposed rate law, the rate-determining step involves the interaction between two negatively charged ion and a polar molecule and thus should correspond to a negative entropy change⁶.

A mechanism based on formation of a soluble complex between enolate anion and Os^{VIII} is suggested. Benzoin has been isolated as the product of oxidation. For the reaction involving interaction between similarly charged ions, the plot of log k_o vs $1/D$ should be a straight line having negative slope. In the present investigation similar results have also been obtained (Fig. 2).

Fig 2 Plot of log k_o vs $1/D$ for hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of deoxybenzoin at 35°

In alkaline medium, Os^{VIII} exists in the equilibrium form of [OsO₄(OH)₂]²⁻. The mechanism proposed involves the formation of enolate anion

of deoxybenzoin with alkali and then a complex is formed between the enolate and $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$. This complex then rapidly decomposes to give benzoin and Os^{VI} ion, and subsequently Os^{VIII} ion is regenerated by the oxidation of Os^{VI} by two molecules of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion.

On the basis of this mechanism and applying steady state approximation,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/dt \\ &= \frac{k_3 k_4 [\text{deoxybenzoin}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-3} + k_4 [\text{OH}^-]} \\ &= \frac{k_3 [\text{deoxybenzoin}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{OH}^-]}{\frac{k_{-3}}{k_4} + [\text{OH}^-]} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Assuming $[\text{OH}^-]$ to be low, such that $k_{-3}/k_4 > [\text{OH}^-]$ and $\{k_{-3}/k_4 + [\text{OH}^-]\} \approx k_{-3}/k_4$, the rate law (6) approximates to equation (7),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_3 k_4}{k_{-3}} [\text{deoxybenzoin}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{OH}^-] \quad (7)$$

At high $[\text{OH}^-]$, $[\text{OH}^-] \gg k_{-3}/k_4$ such that $\{k_{-3}/k_4 + [\text{OH}^-]\} \approx [\text{OH}^-]$. The rate law (6) reduces to rate law (1),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{k_3 [\text{deoxybenzoin}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{OH}^-]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \\ &= k_3 [\text{deoxybenzoin}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Thus equations (7) and (8) explain the experimental results, i.e. first order and zero order dependence of the rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$ at low and high $[\text{OH}^-]$ respectively.

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